

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

UNEVEN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT AS A SIGNIFICANT CHALLENGE AMONG GEORGIA'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEMS

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Abstract

A significant part of the country's socio-economic development challenges is focused on addressing the existing inequalities and disparities between regions. The uneven development of territorial-administrative units in Georgia and the diversity of socio-economic problems are a 'legacy' of the Soviet economic system. After gaining independence, the management and planning of territorial units, along with a number of other reforms, were poorly implemented. As a result of these mistakes, the economic development inequalities between regions deepened and became more pronounced. To the existing socio-economic problems were added entirely new ethnic conflicts and separatist movements, encouraged and „suggested“ by external forces... In the 1990s, these events significantly worsened the socio-economic situation of several regions. The problem became widespread, giving rise to depressed, crisis-stricken, and conflict-affected territories. As a result of the August 2008 Russia-Georgia war, the problems further intensified, and the socio-economic and political life of several regions became significantly more complicated. Terms such as: occupied, border' strategic, and potentially dangerous territories have been used for some time. To overcome the existing problem, the country's strategic development programs need to pay particular and greater attention to the main and targeted measures aimed at 'mitigating' the causes of inequality among territorial-administrative units. It is essential not only to identify the problems but also to resolve them and eliminate them in a short period of time. Regional development inequalities have a significant impact on the country's economic growth and, consequently, on its economic development indicators. Alongside local-territorial capacities, the country's national values, as well as geopolitical developments and changes, must be taken into account.

Keywords: regional inequality, economic growth and development of regions, government programs for regional development.

Considerable successful experience has been accumulated worldwide regarding the effective management of countries' territorial-administrative units. It should also be noted that, alongside the abundance of successful models, certain specific characteristics must be taken into account when addressing the problems of each particular region. A successful model cannot be universally applied like a 'recipe,' because the main and decisive factor for development is the country's real capacities: natural conditions, geographical-territorial characteristics, and the specific features of its historical, cultural, economic, and entrepreneurial environment. Accordingly, within a region, as a territorial part of the country, there cannot be trends and challenges that are sharply different from the country's overall economic development. "By optimally aligning the development of each region (territory) with the overall state objectives, a unified process of mutual interests is formed, creating an environment that facilitates the achievement of national goals" (Grdzlishvili, 2020, p. 44). That is precisely why the economic growth and development of territorial-administrative units is inconceivable without the full-scale development of the country. Accordingly, the main directions and challenges of this process are reflected in the government programs for regional development of the country, which are shaped into targeted development programs for each region. It serves as one of the important and

primary instruments for accomplishing the main objective. The pronounced disparities between regions are the result of problems accumulated over many years, originating from the socialist economic system. Eliminating the underlying causes is not an easy task, as they have developed over a long period. Over time, a foundation was laid for the strengthening of individual regions (territories), which was accompanied by numerous negative consequences:

1. During the socialist economic system, the concentration and clustering of enterprises mostly occurred in large industrial cities, particularly in Tbilisi.
2. „The formation of “mono-cities,” based solely on the development of one or two sectors, made the entire economic progress of these cities dependent on them.
3. A general economic crisis, which is also distinguished by regional particularities.
4. Changes in the country's geopolitical location (Gdzlishvili, 2020, p. 220).

For Georgia, stable economic growth, and consequently economic development, is a key objective, which is directly affected by the pronounced disparities and disproportions between regions. Over the past decade (since 2014), entirely new challenges and obligations have emerged following the signing of the Association Agreement with the European Union, which is linked to the introduction of new norms, standards, and

regulations in the country. The priority issues for addressing regional problems are considered to be: the development of scientifically grounded socio-economic development programs for regions with self-sufficient households, which, based on existing potential, can maximize the full utilization of resources; the establishment of close reproductive linkages between existing sectors and enterprises in the region; the rational use of all major resources maintained through coordinated actions of structural units across various sectors; and the formation of territorial entities with social priorities, taking into account the economic and geographical potential.

A significant change in the current situation will occur only if the state primarily shifts its attention to regional issues. It should be noted that a region cannot tackle severe socio-economic problems on its own. On

the contrary, over time, due to difficult social conditions, unemployment, insufficient job opportunities, and a range of other problems, addressing the issues of territories depleted of young generations faces numerous obstacles. It is impossible to substantially resolve the problems through small-scale proposed social programs and packages. Unfortunately, against this backdrop, the number of lagging, crisis-affected, and depressed regions in the country is increasing. They are characterized by underdeveloped infrastructure and a lack of social service provisions. The disparities present in the regions have their own underlying factors and causes. The greatest problem is unemployment, which directly affects income and, consequently, the standard of living. A comparison of the distribution of gross domestic product (GDP) and unemployment rates across the country's regions clearly reveals the differences and inequalities between them.

Table 1

Distribution of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (million GEL) By Regions of Georgia

Regions of Georgia	2014 (year)	2024 (year)
Tbilisi	14,155.40	42,982.60
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	1,737.20	4,441.80
Racha-Lechkhumi, Kvemo Svaneti	138, 6	476,8
Imereti	2,265.10	6,270.60
Guria	544,2	1,357.40
Autonomous Republic of Adjara	2,325.10	7,516.20
Samtskhe-Javakheti	1,118.10	2,485.80
Shida Kartli	1,513.70	3,414.90
Kvemo Kartli	2,060.90	5,778.70
Mtskheta Mtianeti	677,8	2,216.20
Kakheti	1, 546.10	4,038.50
Georgia	28,082.10	80,979.40

Table 2

Unemployment rate (%) By regions of Georgia

Regions of Georgia	2014 (year)	2024 (year)
Tbilisi	22,4	14,9
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	24,9	10,5
Racha-Lechkhumi, Kvemo Svaneti	17	11, 6
Imereti	22,5	17,3
Guria	20,0	16,3
Autonomous Republic of Adjara	38,6	11,3
Samtskhe-Javakheti	10,5	7,7
Shida Kartli	20	14,3
Kvemo Kartli	15,3	16,7
Mtskheta Mtianeti	16,3	13,6
Kakheti	19,6	10,2
Georgia	23	13,9

Source: National Statistics Office of Georgia

Georgia is a small country, but its regions differ sharply in a number of characteristics, which over time has been reflected in the development of their structures. During the transitional period to a market economy, the prolonged process highlighted and even deepened many problems. Over the years, biases, influences, lobbying, governmental "favoritism" toward certain regions, and their exceptional status became evident in the allocation of financial resources. In our view, in order to mitigate the existing disproportions

and unequal outcomes, it is necessary, when allocating funding, to:

- Promote the interests of the regions, prioritizing them and providing appropriate financial support, targeting funding, and establishing specific directions
- Find long-term and stable financial sources
- Identify specific regional investment projects and continuously monitoring their financial support
- Take into account regional characteristics and specificities during the implementation of reforms, and

ensuring equal conditions when carrying out investment activities

Despite the significant work carried out in recent years, many problems have accumulated, accompanied by a number of challenges and difficulties. An unstable political environment negatively affects the development of several regions, with most of them still largely dependent on local resources and sources of funding. The targeting, effectiveness, purpose, and directions of the investments made are not fully monitored. In many regions, investments and appropriate funding are still allocated only in particularly severe cases.

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